

The role of waves in producing DNA anomalies

Alireza Sepehri *

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Up to date, it has been known that some anomalies in DNA states are the main cause of some diseases like the cancer, however the origin of these anomalies is unclear. In this research, we propose a mathematical model which considers the effect of waves in producing anomaly within DNA structures. In this model, a DNA emits two types of waves. 1. Electromagnetic 2. Ultrasound waves. These waves interact with DNAs within other cells. Sometimes, these waves are carried by some external waves and become more stronger. These strong waves interact with some DNAs and produce some DNA-like holes in liquid within cells. Some waves force to DNA polymerases and lead them towards DNA holes. Consequently, DNA-holes are replicated and some new DNA states are produced. These new DNA states create some extra cells and may lead to the cancer. The probability for producing anomaly within cells depend on the wavelength of external waves. This probability is zero for radio waves and near to 1 for nano-meter waves.

Keywords: Cancer, DNA, hole, Wave, Anomaly, States

I. INTRODUCTION

The role of waves in evolutions of DNA and its damages have been considered extensively. For example, Montagnier and his collaborators have argued that bacterial and viral DNAs could produce some frequencies of electromagnetic waves [1]. They have considered the experimental conditions by which electromagnetic signals (EMS) of low frequency can be emitted by diluted aqueous solutions of these bacterial and viral DNAs [2]. Some authors have argued that electromagnetic signals are endogenously emerged at different levels of the biological organization and, likely, have an active role in synchronizing internal cell function or local/systemic adaptive response. Consequently, each adaptive response can be considered by its specific electromagnetic signature and, therefore, correlates with a unique and specific electromagnetic wave [3]. In another research, it has been found that electromagnetic signals recorded from viral and bacterial DNA solutions are consistent with the gauge theory paradigm of quantum fields. It has been argued that London dispersion forces between delocalized electrons of base pairs of DNA are responsible for the formation of dipole modes that can be recognized by Taq polymerase in PCR [4]. In another paper, authors have reported that 3D-A-DNA structure behaves as a fractal antenna, which can interact with the electromagnetic fields over a wide range of frequencies. Using the lattice details of human DNA, they have modeled radiation of DNA as a helical antenna [5]. In another work, authors have suggested that Resonant Recognition Model is a powerful model that can computationally consider protein, DNA and RNA electromagnetic resonances [7]. In another investigation, a mathematical model for electronic structure of DNA has been proposed and its structure have been compared with AM and FM radio receivers/senders [7]. Also, in another article, a model for exchanging waves between DNAs and molecules of water has been proposed and have been shown that DNA waves could interact with pure water and change its entropy and quantum spectrum [8]. Motivated by these researches, we propose a mathematical model to consider the role of external waves in emergency of anomaly in DNA states.

This paper consists of two main parts. In section II, we consider the process of the emergence of anomaly in DNA states by waves. In section III, we obtain the probability for producing anomaly in DNA states in terms of wavelengths.

II. EMERGENCE OF ANOMALY IN DNA STATES BY EXTERNAL WAVES

A DNA could emit two types of waves: 1. Electromagnetic waves 2. Ultrasound waves. This is because that a DNA is built from charged particles and by each motion, charges move. According to laws of physics, by motion of charged particles, some electromagnetic waves are emerged. On the other hand, a DNA coils several time around different axes and acts like one inductor. This inductor interacts with nuclear membrane and cause to its motion. This membrane acts like the plastic in one speaker/microphone and cause to motion of particles. By motion of particles, some currents are produced. These currents produce some new electromagnetic waves. These electromagnetic waves interact with

* alireza.sepehri3@gmail.com

DNA inductors and move them. These DNA inductors produce another waves and move nuclear membranes again. By motion of nuclear membranes, some longitudinal waves are emerged which play the role of ultrasound waves (See figure 1).

FIG. 1: A DNA within nucleus is similar to the inductor within a speaker.

When ultrasound waves reach to a cell membrane, produce an un-stability between charged particles within cell and out of it. These un-stability leads to the motion of charged particles and production of more stronger waves. These waves interact with charged particles on the nuclear membranes and lead to their motions. By motion of charged particles within the nucleus, new strong waves are produced. These waves interact with DNA inductors and move them. By motion of DNA inductors, some waves are emerged (See Figure 2). These waves move biological matters within the nucleus and produce some hexagonal/pentagonal holes (See Figure 3). To fill these holes, some new bases are emerged. These new bases increase number of states within a DNA and leads to the emergence of some diseases.

To count number of microstates of a DNA, we use of some concepts in string theory. In this model, each DNA is built from hexagonal and pentagonal molecules. On the other hand, atoms in each of these molecules are connected by a string-like field (See Figure 4). This field can be written in terms of other normal fields.

$$X^I \approx y^I + y_J F^{IJ} - y_J R^{IJ} + y_J \partial^I \phi \partial^J \phi - i y_J \bar{\psi} \gamma^J \partial^I \psi + \dots$$

$$I = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6 \quad (1)$$

where X^I is the string fields, F^{IJ} is the two form photonic field strength, R^{IJ} is the gravitational field, ψ is the fermionic field, ϕ is the scalar field and y_J is the coordinate. We can write photonic field and gravitational wave as below:

$$F^{IJ} = \partial^I A^J - \partial^J A^I,$$

$$R_{IJ} = \partial_I \Gamma_{JB}^B - \partial_J \Gamma_{IB}^B + \Gamma_{JB}^A \Gamma_{IA}^B - \Gamma_{IB}^A \Gamma_{JA}^B,$$

$$\Gamma_{IJK} = \partial_I g_{JK} + \partial_K g_{IJ} - \partial_J g_{IK}, \quad (2)$$

where A is the one form photonic field and g is the metric field. We can write below equation for communications between strings:

$$\{X^I, X^J\} = \Sigma_{I,J} \varepsilon^{I'J'} \frac{\partial X^I}{\partial y^{I'}} \frac{\partial X^J}{\partial y^{J'}}$$

FIG. 2: External waves interact with cell and nuclear membranes, move them and produce some new waves.

FIG. 3: External waves interact with DNAs, move them and produce some holes

FIG. 4: String-like fields connect atoms in hexagonal and pentagonal bases.

$$= F^{IJ} - R^{IJ} + \partial^I \phi \partial^J \phi - i\bar{\psi} \gamma^J \partial^I \psi + \dots \quad (3)$$

It is clear that this communication depends on the photonic, gravitational, scalar and fermionic fields. This means that string-like fields between two atoms in a hexagonal/pentagonal base is formed from photons, gravitons, scalars and fermions. Generalizing above two dimensional communication to four gives us:

$$\begin{aligned} DNA^{IJKLMN} &= \{X^I, X^J, X^K, X^L, X^M, X^N\} \\ &= \varepsilon^{I'J'K'L'M'N'} \frac{\partial X^I}{\partial y^{I'}} \frac{\partial X^J}{\partial y^{J'}} \frac{\partial X^K}{\partial y^{K'}} \frac{\partial X^L}{\partial y^{L'}} \frac{\partial X^M}{\partial y^{M'}} \frac{\partial X^N}{\partial y^{N'}} \\ &\Downarrow \\ &= \int d^4x \sqrt{g} (DNA_{IJKLMN} DNA^{IJKLMN}) \\ &= \int d^4x \sqrt{g} \left(\varepsilon_{I'J'K'L'M'N'} \frac{\partial X_{I'}}{\partial y_{I'}} \frac{\partial X_{J'}}{\partial y_{J'}} \frac{\partial X_{K'}}{\partial y_{K'}} \frac{\partial X_{L'}}{\partial y_{L'}} \frac{\partial X_{M'}}{\partial y_{M'}} \frac{\partial X_{N'}}{\partial y_{N'}} \times \right. \\ &\quad \left. \varepsilon^{I''J''K''L''M''N''} \frac{\partial X^{I''}}{\partial y^{I''}} \frac{\partial X^{J''}}{\partial y^{J''}} \frac{\partial X^{K''}}{\partial y^{K''}} \frac{\partial X^{L''}}{\partial y^{L''}} \frac{\partial X^{M''}}{\partial y^{M''}} \frac{\partial X^{N''}}{\partial y^{N''}} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Where DNA^{IJKLMN} is six form field which is exchanged between a base from a DNA to a base from a RNA or DNA. This field is formed from joining string fields. Also, there are another five form field which can be coupled to

above six form field and make it stable. This form field can be reduced to a circle with a constant energy. We can show:

$$\begin{aligned}
X^I &\approx y^I + y_J F^{IJ} - y_J R^{IJ} + y_J \partial^I \phi \partial^J \phi - i y_J \bar{\psi} \gamma^J \partial^I \psi + \dots \\
&\Downarrow \\
\frac{\partial X^{I_5}}{\partial y^{I_5}} &\approx \delta(y^{I_5}) + \dots \quad \frac{\partial X^{I_6}}{\partial y^{I_6}} \approx \delta(y^{I_6}) + \dots \quad \frac{\partial X^{I_7}}{\partial y^{I_7}} \approx \delta(y^{I_7}) + \dots, \\
\int_{M^{N=5}} &\rightarrow \int_{y^{I_5}+y^{I_6}+y^{I_7}+y^{I_8}+y^{I_9}} \epsilon^{I'_5 I'_6 I'_7 I'_8 I'_9} \frac{\partial X^{I_5}}{\partial y^{I'_5}} \frac{\partial X^{I_6}}{\partial y^{I'_6}} \frac{\partial X^{I_7}}{\partial y^{I'_7}} \frac{\partial X^{I_8}}{\partial y^{I'_8}} \frac{\partial X^{I_9}}{\partial y^{I'_9}} = 1 + \dots, \quad (5)
\end{aligned}$$

Multiplying six form and five form fields, we can write an stable action for the interaction between bases of a DNA or bases of two different DNAs and RNAs:

$$\begin{aligned}
&\int_{M^{N=5}} \int_{M^6} \sqrt{g} \left(DNA_{I_1 I_2 I_3 I_4} DNA^{I_1 I_2 I_3 I_4} \right) \\
&= \int_{M^6 + y^{I_7} + y^{I_8} + y^{I_9} + y^{I_{10}} + y^{I_{11}}} \sqrt{g} \epsilon^{I'_7 I'_8 I'_9 I'_{10} I'_{11}} DNA_{I_1 I_2 I_3 I_4 I_5 I_6} DNA^{I_1 I_2 I_3 I_4 I_5 I_6} \times \\
&\quad \frac{\partial X^{I_7}}{\partial y^{I'_7}} \frac{\partial X^{I_8}}{\partial y^{I'_8}} \frac{\partial X^{I_9}}{\partial y^{I'_9}} \frac{\partial X^{I_{10}}}{\partial y^{I'_{10}}} \frac{\partial X^{I_{11}}}{\partial y^{I'_{11}}}, \quad (6)
\end{aligned}$$

Extra five form field can produce a pentagonal hole within liquid around a DNA. This hole can be field with biological matters and a new bases could be created. Thus, we can write:

$$Hole^{I_7 I_8 I_9 I_{10} I_{11}} = \epsilon^{I'_7 I'_8 I'_9 I'_{10} I'_{11}} \frac{\partial X^{I_7}}{\partial y^{I'_7}} \frac{\partial X^{I_8}}{\partial y^{I'_8}} \frac{\partial X^{I_9}}{\partial y^{I'_9}} \frac{\partial X^{I_{10}}}{\partial y^{I'_{10}}} \frac{\partial X^{I_{11}}}{\partial y^{I'_{11}}}, \quad (7)$$

FIG. 5: A RNA/DNA hole could be produced by external waves.

These base-like holes could be joined to each other and form a RNA or extra DNA (See figure 5). Thus, holes could be main cause of the emergence of cancer or other diseases. Thus, the interaction between bases of a DNA or a DNA and a RNA could be presented with below action:

$$S_{DNA-DNA-Hole}^{N=6+5} = \int_{M^6 + y^{I_7} + y^{I_8} + y^{I_9} + y^{I_{10}} + y^{I_{11}}} \sqrt{g} DNA_{I_1 I_2 I_3 I_4 I_5 I_6} DNA^{I_1 I_2 I_3 I_4 I_5 I_6} Hole^{I_7 I_8 I_9 I_{10} I_{11}}. \quad (8)$$

To consider stability of above action, we should obtain its variation. For an stable action, this variation should be equal to zero. For example, we calculate variation of hole field and obtain:

$$\begin{aligned}
X^I &\approx y^I + y_J F^{IJ} - y_J R^{IJ} + y_J \partial^I \phi \partial^J \phi - i y_J \bar{\psi} \gamma^J \partial^I \psi + \dots \\
&\Downarrow \\
\frac{\partial \delta_A X^I}{\partial y^I} &= \delta(y^I) \\
&\Downarrow \\
\int_{M^{N=5+M^6}} \delta_A Hole^{I_7 I_8 I_9 I_{10} I_{11}} &= \int_{M^{N=5+M^6}} \Sigma_{I'_7 I'_8 I'_9 I'_{10} I'_{11}} \varepsilon^{I'_7 I'_8 I'_9 I'_{10} I'_{11}} \times \\
&\delta_A \left(\frac{\partial X^{I_7}}{\partial y^{I'_7}} \frac{\partial X^{I_8}}{\partial y^{I'_8}} \frac{\partial X^{I_9}}{\partial y^{I'_9}} \frac{\partial X^{I_{10}}}{\partial y^{I'_{10}}} \frac{\partial X^{I_{11}}}{\partial y^{I'_{11}}} \right) \\
&= \int_{M^{N=5+M^6}} \Sigma_{I'_8 I'_9 I'_{10} I'_{11}} \varepsilon^{I'_8 I'_9 I'_{10} I'_{11}} \times \\
&\left(\frac{\partial X^{I_8}}{\partial y^{I'_8}} \frac{\partial X^{I_9}}{\partial y^{I'_9}} \frac{\partial X^{I_{10}}}{\partial y^{I'_{10}}} \frac{\partial X^{I_{11}}}{\partial y^{I'_{11}}} \right) \\
&= \int_{M^{N=5+M^6}} (F^{IJ} - R^{IJ} + \partial^I \phi \partial^J \phi - i \bar{\psi} \gamma^J \partial^I \psi + \dots) \\
&\times (F_{IJ} - R_{IJ} + \partial_I \phi \partial_J \phi - i \bar{\psi} \gamma_J \partial_I \psi + \dots). \tag{9}
\end{aligned}$$

Thus, variation of hole fields give photonic, gravitational, scalar and dirac fields. We calculate the variation for the action between bases of a DNA or two different DNAs:

$$\begin{aligned}
\delta S_{\text{DNA-DNA}}^{N=6+5} &= \int_{M^6+M^{N=5}} \sqrt{g} \Sigma_{n=1}^{11} \left(\text{tr} F^n - \text{tr} R^n + \text{tr} F^n R^{11-n} + \text{tr} [\partial_I \phi \partial^I \phi]^n \right. \\
&- \text{tr} [\bar{\psi} \gamma_J \partial_I \psi]^n + \text{tr} [\partial_I \phi \partial^I \phi]^n R^{11-n} + \text{tr} [\partial_I \phi \partial^I \phi]^n F^{11-n} \\
&- \text{tr} [\bar{\psi} \gamma_J \partial_I \psi]^n R^{11-n} - \text{tr} [\bar{\psi} \gamma_J \partial_I \psi]^n F^{11-n} \\
&\left. - \text{tr} [\bar{\psi} \gamma_J \partial_I \psi]^n [\partial_I \phi \partial^I \phi]^{11-n} \right). \tag{10}
\end{aligned}$$

Above variation isnt zero and for this reason, we regard the coupling of hole fields to bases of DNAs and obtain the variation again:

$$\begin{aligned}
\delta S_{\text{DNA-DNA-Hole}}^{N=6+5} &= - \int_{M^6+M^{N=5}} \sqrt{g} \Sigma_{n=1}^{11} \left(\text{tr} F^n - \text{tr} R^n + \text{tr} F^n R^{11-n} + \text{tr} [\partial_I \phi \partial^I \phi]^n \right. \\
&- \text{tr} [\bar{\psi} \gamma_J \partial_I \psi]^n + \text{tr} [\partial_I \phi \partial^I \phi]^n R^{11-n} + \text{tr} [\partial_I \phi \partial^I \phi]^n F^{11-n} \\
&- \text{tr} [\bar{\psi} \gamma_J \partial_I \psi]^n R^{11-n} - \text{tr} [\bar{\psi} \gamma_J \partial_I \psi]^n F^{11-n} \\
&\left. - \text{tr} [\bar{\psi} \gamma_J \partial_I \psi]^n [\partial_I \phi \partial^I \phi]^{11-n} \right) \\
&\times (1 + F^{IJ} - R^{IJ} + \partial^I \phi \partial^J \phi - i \bar{\psi} \gamma^J \partial^I \psi + \dots) \\
&\times (1 + F_{IJ} - R_{IJ} + \partial_I \phi \partial_J \phi - i \bar{\psi} \gamma_J \partial_I \psi + \dots). \tag{11}
\end{aligned}$$

This variation isnt zero and thus, we have some extra terms within total action. These extra fields could be obtain from the variation of actions:

$$\delta S_{\text{DNA-DNA-Hole}}^{N=6+5} + \delta S_{\text{DNA-DNA}}^{N=6+5}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= - \int_{M^6+M^{N=5}} \sqrt{g} \Sigma_{n=1}^{11} \left(\text{tr} F^n - \text{tr} R^n + \text{tr} F^n R^{11-n} + \text{tr} [\partial_I \phi \partial^I \phi]^n \right. \\
&\quad - \text{tr} [\bar{\psi} \gamma_J \partial_I \psi]^n + \text{tr} [\partial_I \phi \partial^I \phi]^n R^{11-n} + \text{tr} [\partial_I \phi \partial^I \phi]^n F^{11-n} \\
&\quad - \text{tr} [\bar{\psi} \gamma_J \partial_I \psi]^n R^{11-n} - \text{tr} [\bar{\psi} \gamma_J \partial_I \psi]^n F^{11-n} \\
&\quad \left. - \text{tr} [\bar{\psi} \gamma_J \partial_I \psi]^n [\partial_I \phi \partial^I \phi]^{11-n} \right) \\
&\quad \times (F^{IJ} - R^{IJ} + \partial^I \phi \partial^J \phi - i \bar{\psi} \gamma^J \partial^I \psi + \dots) \\
&\quad \times (F_{IJ} - R_{IJ} + \partial_I \phi \partial_J \phi - i \bar{\psi} \gamma_J \partial_I \psi + \dots). \tag{12}
\end{aligned}$$

Above variation produce some extra photonic, gravitational, scalar and fermionic fields. Regarding these extra terms, we can write total action:

$$\begin{aligned}
S_{\text{tot}}^{N=6+5} &= S_{\text{DNA-DNA-Hole}}^{N=6+5} + S_{\text{DNA-DNA}}^{N=6+5} + S_{\text{Anomaly}}^{N=6+5} \\
S_{\text{Anomaly}}^{N=6+5} &= - \int_{M^6+M^{N=5}} \sqrt{g} \Sigma_{n=1}^{11} \left(\text{tr} F^n - \text{tr} R^n + \text{tr} F^n R^{11-n} + \text{tr} [\partial_I \phi \partial^I \phi]^n \right. \\
&\quad - \text{tr} [\bar{\psi} \gamma_J \partial_I \psi]^n + \text{tr} [\partial_I \phi \partial^I \phi]^n R^{11-n} + \text{tr} [\partial_I \phi \partial^I \phi]^n F^{11-n} \\
&\quad - \text{tr} [\bar{\psi} \gamma_J \partial_I \psi]^n R^{11-n} - \text{tr} [\bar{\psi} \gamma_J \partial_I \psi]^n F^{11-n} \\
&\quad \left. - \text{tr} [\bar{\psi} \gamma_J \partial_I \psi]^n [\partial_I \phi \partial^I \phi]^{11-n} \right) \\
&\quad \times (F^{IJ} - R^{IJ} + \partial^I \phi \partial^J \phi - i \bar{\psi} \gamma^J \partial^I \psi + \dots) \\
&\quad \times (F_{IJ} - R_{IJ} + \partial_I \phi \partial_J \phi - i \bar{\psi} \gamma_J \partial_I \psi + \dots). \tag{13}
\end{aligned}$$

where $S_{\text{Anomaly}}^{N=6+5}$ is the action of anomaly and depends on extra photons, gravitons, scalars and fermions. Assuming that fields are small, we can use of taylor expansion and rewrite above action as:

$$\begin{aligned}
S_{\text{Anomaly}}^{N=6+5} &= - \int_{M^6+M^{N=5}} \sqrt{g} \Sigma_{n=1}^{11} \left[\left(1 + 2 \text{tr} F^n - 2 \text{tr} R^n + 2 \text{tr} F^n R^{11-n} + 2 \text{tr} [\partial_I \phi \partial^I \phi]^n \right. \right. \\
&\quad - 2 \text{tr} [\bar{\psi} \gamma_J \partial_I \psi]^n + 2 \text{tr} [\partial_I \phi \partial^I \phi]^n R^{11-n} + 2 \text{tr} [\partial_I \phi \partial^I \phi]^n F^{11-n} \\
&\quad - 2 \text{tr} [\bar{\psi} \gamma_J \partial_I \psi]^n R^{11-n} - 2 \text{tr} [\bar{\psi} \gamma_J \partial_I \psi]^n F^{11-n} \\
&\quad \left. \left. - 2 \text{tr} [\bar{\psi} \gamma_J \partial_I \psi]^n [\partial_I \phi \partial^I \phi]^{11-n} \right) U \right]^{1/2} \\
&\quad U = (F^{IJ} - R^{IJ} + \partial^I \phi \partial^J \phi - i \bar{\psi} \gamma^J \partial^I \psi + \dots) \\
&\quad \times (F_{IJ} - R_{IJ} + \partial_I \phi \partial_J \phi - i \bar{\psi} \gamma_J \partial_I \psi + \dots). \tag{14}
\end{aligned}$$

We assume that scalar field depends on the separation distance between two bases "Z" (See figure 4). Thus, we can write:

$$\begin{aligned}
S_{\text{Anomaly}}^{N=6+5} &= - \int_{M^6+M^{N=5}} \sqrt{g} \Sigma_{n=1}^{11} \left[\left(1 + 2 \text{tr} F^n - 2 \text{tr} R^n + 2 \text{tr} F^n R^{11-n} + 2[Z']^{2n} \right. \right. \\
&\quad - 2 \text{tr} [\bar{\psi} \gamma_J \partial_I \psi]^n + 2[Z']^{2n} R^{11-n} + 2[Z']^{2n} F^{11-n} \\
&\quad - 2 \text{tr} [\bar{\psi} \gamma_J \partial_I \psi]^n R^{11-n} - 2 \text{tr} [\bar{\psi} \gamma_J \partial_I \psi]^n F^{11-n} \\
&\quad \left. \left. - 2 \text{tr} [\bar{\psi} \gamma_J \partial_I \psi]^n [Z']^{11-2n} \right) U \right]^{1/2} \\
&\quad U = (F^{IJ} - R^{IJ} + \partial^I \phi \partial^J \phi - i \bar{\psi} \gamma^J \partial^I \psi + \dots) \\
&\quad \times (F_{IJ} - R_{IJ} + \partial_I \phi \partial_J \phi - i \bar{\psi} \gamma_J \partial_I \psi + \dots). \tag{15}
\end{aligned}$$

Previously, a method for calculating the Hamiltonian for above action has been proposed. Using the method in [7], we can obtain the Hamiltonian as:

$$H_{\text{Anomaly}}^{N=6+5} = - \int_{M^6+M^{N=5}} \sqrt{g} \Sigma_{n=1}^{11} \left(1 + 2[Z']^{2n} \right)^{1/2} \times$$

$$\Sigma_{i,j} \left[1 + \frac{K^2}{l_F^4}\right]^{-i/2} \left[1 + \frac{K^2}{l_R^4}\right]^{-j/2} \left[1 + \frac{K^2}{l_\psi^4}\right]^{-11/2+i/2+j/2} \quad (16)$$

where l_F is the separation distance which is produced by photons between two bases, l_R is the separation distance which is produced by gravitons between two bases and l_ψ is the separation distance which is produced by fermions between two bases. Also, K is the constant and Z is the real separation distance between two bases. This anomaly corresponds to extra bases which produced by waves within the liquid around a DNA. To count total energy of anomaly, we should regard all interactions:

$$\begin{aligned} E_{\text{DNA,Anomaly}}^{N=6+5} &= \Pi_{n=1}^N [H_{\text{Anomaly}}^{N=6+5}]^n \\ &= -\Pi_{n=1}^N \left[\int_{M^6+M^N=5} \sqrt{g} \Sigma_{n=1}^{11} \left(1 + 2[Z']^{2n}\right)^{1/2} \times \right. \\ &\quad \left. \Sigma_{i,j} \left[1 + \frac{K^2}{l_F^4}\right]^{-i/2} \left[1 + \frac{K^2}{l_R^4}\right]^{-j/2} \left[1 + \frac{K^2}{l_\psi^4}\right]^{-11/2+i/2+j/2} \right]^n \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

Using above equation, we can obtain the entropy of states of anomaly:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{entropy}_{\text{DNA,Anomaly}}^{N=6+5} &= \frac{1}{T} E_{\text{DNA,Anomaly}}^{N=6+5} \\ &= \frac{1}{T} \Pi_{n=1}^N [H_{\text{Anomaly}}^{N=6+5}]^n \\ &= -\frac{1}{T} \Pi_{n=1}^N \left[\int_{M^6+M^N=5} \sqrt{g} \Sigma_{n=1}^{11} \left(1 + 2[Z']^{2n}\right)^{1/2} \times \right. \\ &\quad \left. \Sigma_{i,j} \left[1 + \frac{K^2}{l_F^4}\right]^{-i/2} \left[1 + \frac{K^2}{l_R^4}\right]^{-j/2} \left[1 + \frac{K^2}{l_\psi^4}\right]^{-11/2+i/2+j/2} \right]^n \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

Using above entropy, we can obtain total number of micro-states of an anomaly:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{entropy}_{\text{DNA,Anomaly}}^{N=6+5} &= K \ln \Omega_{\text{DNA,Anomaly}}^{N=6+5} \\ \Omega_{\text{DNA,Anomaly}}^{N=6+5} &\sim e^{\text{entropy}_{\text{DNA,Anomaly}}^{N=6+5}} \\ &= \exp \left[\frac{1}{T} \Pi_{n=1}^N [H_{\text{Anomaly}}^{N=6+5}]^n \right] \\ &= \exp \left[-\frac{1}{T} \Pi_{n=1}^N \left[\int_{M^6+M^N=5} \sqrt{g} \Sigma_{n=1}^{11} \left(1 + 2[Z']^{2n}\right)^{1/2} \Sigma_{i,j} \left[1 + \frac{K^2}{l_F^4}\right]^{-i/2} \left[1 + \frac{K^2}{l_R^4}\right]^{-j/2} \left[1 + \frac{K^2}{l_\psi^4}\right]^{-11/2+i/2+j/2} \right]^n \right] \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

Above equation shows that total number of microstates of anomaly around a DNA depends on the separation distance between bases, the strength of external photonic, gravitational, scalar and fermionic fields. By increasing the strength of external fields, more holes are emerged and to fill them, some extra matters are produced. These matters fill holes and produce some extra bases. These bases are origins of anomaly.

III. THE PROBABILITY FOR PRODUCING ANOMALY IN DNA STATES

In previous section, we have shown that waves could produce some anomaly in DNA states. In fact, they produce some holes in liquid around a DNA. These holes have the hexagonal and pentagonal shapes. By joining these holes, some DNA and RNA-like structures are emerged. On the other hand, some waves force to DNA polymerases and put them on DNA holes (See figure 6). Consequently, DNA holes are replicated and some real extra DNAs are emerged (See figure 7). These new DNAs produce some extra cells. These extra cells grow independently and don't obey of normal mechanism in a human/animal's body. Consequently, some extra cells are emerged that play the role of cancerous cells.

Replacing wavelenghts $\lambda_{F/R/\psi}$ by separation distance $l_{F/R/\psi}$ in equation (19) gives:

$$\Omega_{\text{DNA,Anomaly}}^{N=6+5} \sim e^{\text{entropy}_{\text{DNA,Anomaly}}^{N=6+5}}$$

FIG. 6: A DNA polymerase could act on DNA holes.

FIG. 7: DNA holes could be replicated and a new DNA is emerged.

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \exp \left[\frac{1}{T} \prod_{n=1}^N [H_{\text{Anomaly}}^{N=6+5}]^n \right] \\
 &= \exp \left[-\frac{1}{T} \prod_{n=1}^N \left[\int_{M^6+M^N=5} \sqrt{g} \Sigma_{n=1}^{11} \left(1 + 2[Z']^{2n} \right)^{1/2} \Sigma_{i,j} \left[1 + \frac{K^2}{\lambda_F^4} \right]^{-i/2} \left[1 + \frac{K^2}{\lambda_R^4} \right]^{-j/2} \left[1 + \frac{K^2}{\lambda_\psi^4} \right]^{-11/2+i/2+j/2} \right]^n \right] \quad (20)
 \end{aligned}$$

By dividing above number of microstates for anomaly to total number of microstates, we can calculate the probability for producing anomaly:

$$\begin{aligned}
 P_{\text{DNA,Anomaly}}^{N=6+5} &\sim \Omega_{\text{DNA,Anomaly}}^{N=6+5} / \Omega_{\text{DNA,tot}}^{N=6+5} \\
 &= \frac{1}{\Omega_{\text{DNA,tot}}^{N=6+5}} \exp \left[\frac{1}{T} \prod_{n=1}^N [H_{\text{Anomaly}}^{N=6+5}]^n \right] \\
 &= \frac{1}{\Omega_{\text{DNA,tot}}^{N=6+5}} \exp \left[-\frac{1}{T} \prod_{n=1}^N \left[\int_{M^6+M^N=5} \sqrt{g} \Sigma_{n=1}^{11} \left(1 + 2[Z']^{2n} \right)^{1/2} \Sigma_{i,j} \left[1 + \frac{K^2}{\lambda_F^4} \right]^{-i/2} \left[1 + \frac{K^2}{\lambda_R^4} \right]^{-j/2} \left[1 + \frac{K^2}{\lambda_\psi^4} \right]^{-11/2+i/2+j/2} \right]^n \right] \quad (21)
 \end{aligned}$$

Above probability shows that by decreasing wavelength, more anomaly states are emerged. In figure 8, we present

FIG. 8: The probability for producing anomaly in terms of wavelength.

the probability for producing anomaly in terms of wavelength. It is clear that radio waves with wavelength around 1-10 meter couldnt pass the cell membranes and has no effect on the evolutions of DNAs. However, millimetre waves have the size of cells and could have few effects on DNAs. By decreasing wavelenghts, this effect increases and nano-meter waves like light waves have many effects on the replications of DNAs.

IV. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

In this search, we have proposed a model to consider the effect of external waves on DNA evolutions. We have shown that waves interact with DNA bases and create some hexagonal and pentagonal holes within the liquid around them. These holes join to each other and form some DNA-like holes. These new holes are replicated by DNA polymerases and some extra DNA states are emerged. These extra DNAs produce extra cells. The probability for producing these extra cells depend on the wavelength and nano-meter waves have more effect on DNA evolutions.

Acknowledgments

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- [1] Luc Montagnier, Jamal Aïssa, Emilio Del Giudice, C Lavallee, A Tedeschi, Giuseppe Vitiello, DNA waves and water , Journal of Physics: Conference Series, 2011, Volume 306, Number 1. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/306/1/012007>.
- [2] Luc Montagnier, Emilio Del Giudice, Jamal Aïssa, Claude Lavallee, Steven Motschwiller, Antonio Capolupo, Albino Polcari, Paola Romano, Alberto Tedeschi, Giuseppe Vitiello, Transduction of DNA information through water and electromagnetic waves, Electromagnetic Biology and Medicine 2015.34:106-112. 10.3109/15368378.2015.1036072.

- [3] Alberto Foletti, Mario Ledda, Maria Grazia Lolli, Settimio Grimaldi , Antonella Lisi (2017) Electromagnetic information transfer through aqueous system, *Electromagnetic Biology and Medicine*, 36:3, 289-294, DOI: 10.1080/15368378.2017.1347882.
- [4] L. Montagnier , J. Aïssa , A. Capolupo , T. J. A. Craddock , P. Kurian , C. Lavallee , A. Polcari , P. Romano, A. Tedeschi and G. Vitiello, Water Bridging Dynamics of Polymerase Chain Reaction in the Gauge Theory Paradigm of Quantum Fields, *Water* 2017, 9(5), 339; <https://doi.org/10.3390/w905033>.
- [5] P. Singh, R. Doti, J. E. Lugo, J. Faubert, S. Rawat, S. Ghosh, K. Ray, A. Bandyopadhyay (2018), DNA as an Electromagnetic Fractal Cavity Resonator: Its Universal Sensing and Fractal Antenna Behavior. In: Pant M., Ray K., Sharma T., Rawat S., Bandyopadhyay A. (eds) *Soft Computing: Theories and Applications. Advances in Intelligent Systems and Computing*, vol 584. Springer, Singapore.
- [6] I.Cosic, D. Cosic, K. Lazar, Is it possible to predict electromagnetic resonances in proteins, DNA and RNA?. *EPJ Nonlinear Biomed Phys* 3, 5 (2015) doi:10.1140/epjnbp/s40366-015-0020-6.
- [7] Alireza Sepehri, A mathematical model for DNA , *International Journal of Geometric Methods in Modern Physics* Vol. 14, No. 11, 1750152 (2017).
- [8] Massimo Fioranelli , Maria Grazia Rocchia, *International Journal of Geometric Methods in Modern Physics*, Volume 16, Issue 4, id. 1950051-1407.10.1142/S0219887819500518